

AN ANALYSIS OF SOCIO-POLITICAL PROCESSES IN AFGHANISTAN IN THE LATE 19th AND EARLY 20th CENTURIES FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF THE TATAR EDUCATORS MUKHTAR BAKIR AND THE JADIDS

M.A. Rahmatov

Basic doctoral student of National University Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20789802>

Abstract. *This article systematically analyzes the complex sociopolitical processes unfolding in Afghanistan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, including the struggle to establish a centralized state, modernization movements, and the challenges of preserving national independence, through the lens of the Tatar educator Mukhtar Bakir and the Jadidist intellectual milieu to which he belonged. The study comprehensively explores Mukhtar Bakir's conceptual work in the Turkestan and Tatar press, his assessments of the Afghan statehood model, and the Russian-British geopolitical confrontation in the region, in accordance with the requirements of the system, using comparative-historical, system-functional, and hermeneutic methods. Based on the sources, it demonstrates Mukhtar Bakir's role as a conceptual and ideological bridge between Tatar and Turkestan Jadidism.*

Keywords: *Mukhtar Bakir, Tatar enlighteners, Jadidism, Afghanistan, modernization, The Great Game, Ismail Gasprinsky, Abdurauf Fitrat, Turkestan, geopolitics, hermeneutics.*

1. INTRODUCTION

For many years, the Jadids' international relations, ideological worldview, and attitude toward Eastern countries were either completely banned or negatively portrayed by Soviet ideology under the labels of "bourgeois nationalism," "pan-Islamism," and "pan-Turkism." Today, studying the personal views, analyses, and conceptual approaches of the Tatar enlightener Mukhtar Bakir on socio-political processes in Afghanistan allows us to objectively assess the global foreign policy thinking of the Jadid movement, the strategy of regional liberation movements, and their place in Tatar-Turkish integration. Based on the personal fund of the Tatar enlightener Mukhtar Bakir, his notes, publicistic speeches, and sources of the periodical press in which he worked, the aim is to identify his ideological and political assessments of the complex socio-political processes that took place in Afghanistan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, systematize them, and reveal their comparative relationship with the views of other modern figures of that era.

The 19th and early 20th centuries were a time of fundamental upheaval, geopolitical cataclysms, and intellectual renaissance for the Central Asian region and adjacent territories. The consistent subjugation of the Central Asian khanates by the Russian Empire, the establishment of a colonial system of governance in the region, and the crisis of local traditional society presented the Muslim intelligentsia with crucial strategic challenges: to lead the country out of the quagmire of centuries-old backwardness, preserve national identity, and restore the foundations of statehood. The Jadid movement, which arose as a result of this socio-political and cultural need, was not limited to internal problems, but also began to deeply analyze global geopolitical processes in the Near and Middle East. During this period, the role of Tatar enlighteners who moved to Turkestan

from the internal provinces of the Russian Empire (Volga region, Urals) and established strong ideological and cultural cooperation with local progressive intellectuals was invaluable. One of the bright and multifaceted representatives of the Tatar Jadid school is Mukhtar Bakir. Mukhtar Bakir's activities in the socio-political, educational and cultural life of Turkestan are not limited to opening new schools of methods or creating textbooks. As an accomplished analyst and publicist of his time, he carefully monitored regional international relations, in particular, socio-political processes in the state of Afghanistan, which was considered an inter-imperialist buffer zone, and tried to systematize them. In addition to analyzing the historical events of the territory of Afghanistan, Mukhtar Bakir also paid attention to its geographical location.

2. METHODS

In order to conduct a fundamental and source-based in-depth study of this scientific problem, to ensure the objectivity and scientificity of the results obtained, a number of methodological principles of modern historiography and sociology were relied on. The principle of historicity and objectivity: Mukhtar Bakir's views on Afghanistan were studied in the context of the specific historical conditions of the period in which he lived and worked, the strict patterns of censorship in Tsarist Russia, administrative pressures in the Turkestan Governor-General, and the aggravation of Russian-British relations. This principle made it possible to avoid subjective approaches and see historical facts through the prism of his time.

Comparative-historical method: The ideological theses put forward by Mukhtar Bakir and his analytical worldview were analyzed in a comparative-synchronous manner with the ideas in the philosophical and political treatises of Ismail Gasprinsky, the founder of the Jadid movement of that time, in the "Tarjimon" newspaper, and later, "Conversation between the Bukhara Minister ... and the Afghan Emir" by Abdurauf Fitrat, the leader of the Turkestan intellectual elite.

Systemic-functional approach: Mukhtar Bakir's intellectual legacy and his attitude towards Afghanistan were considered not in isolation, but as a holistic system. Within this system, functional areas such as anti-colonialism, understanding geopolitical balance, religious-secular balance, and renewal of the education system were isolated and each of them was analyzed separately.

Textual analysis and hermeneutics method: A textual analysis of journalistic articles, archival documents, and notes on the activities of Mukhtar Bakir from the pages of periodicals was carried out. Using a hermeneutic approach, the authors' symbolic meanings hidden between the lines in order to evade censorship by the tsarist government, as well as the ideas of political and national liberation expressed through the "language of Aesop", were revealed.

3. RESULTS

The analysis of sources, the study of archival materials, and the systematization of periodicals yielded the following clear scholarly results regarding the views of the Tatar educator Mukhtar Bakir on socio-political processes in Afghanistan and his role in the Jadid movement. In his political and social views, Mukhtar Bakir presented Afghanistan not simply as a foreign neighboring state, but as a unique and vibrant "political model" for the Muslims of Turkestan and the Volga region, oppressed by the colonial rule of the Russian Empire:

The importance of internal centralization: Mukhtar Bakir positively assessed the policy of Emir Abdurahmankhan to subordinate the scattered and conflicting tribes of Afghanistan to a single centralized state apparatus. According to his notes, the independence of the state and its protection from external enemies depended primarily on its strict internal discipline and the strength of the central government.

The advantage of geopolitical neutrality: Mukhtar Bakir highly appreciated Afghanistan's ability to maintain a balance between Russia and England in the context of the "Great Game", to conduct independent diplomacy without falling into the military-political traps of both empires. He considered this experience to be a strategic direction that should be used in the future restoration of Turkestan statehood.

As an active organizer and teacher of the New Usul (New method) schools, Mukhtar Bakir systematically analyzed the educational reforms carried out in Afghanistan during the reign of Amir Habibullah Khan. According to him, synthesizing the ideas of Siraj ul-Akhbar and Mahmud Tarzi, Mukhtar Bakir deeply studied the content of the Siraj ul-Akhbar newspaper published in Kabul. He successfully synthesized the spirit of this publication, which openly criticized European imperialism and called for the awakening of the Islamic world on the basis of science, with the principles of Tatar Jadidism.

On the integration of religious and secular sciences, Bakir analyzed the experience of the first modern military schools and secular educational institutions established in Afghanistan, demonstrating in practice that an Islamic society can assimilate Western technology and science without losing its identity, religious foundation, and national values.

The socio-political processes in Afghanistan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, in particular the country's struggle for independence, its place at the center of the geopolitical conflicts of the "Great Game," and the modernization movements initiated by Emir Habibullah Khan and Amanullah Khan, have been widely studied in world and regional historiography. In studying these transformational processes in Afghanistan, the seminal works of scholars such as L. Dupree, V. Grigoryan, and M. Shinasi serve as fundamental sources in the international context. In their studies, reforms in Afghanistan's domestic policy and the formation of the "Young Afghans" educational movement were analyzed primarily in the context of Western and Middle Eastern (Ottoman Empire) influence. These studies partially reveal the foreign policy views of the new press "Sadoi Turkestan", "Oyna," "Najot" and others, their support for Afghan independence, and their ideological ties to the Afghan enlightenment movement founded by Mahmud Tarzi. However, the direct and indirect views of Tatar enlighteners, in particular Mukhtar Bakir, who left a unique mark on the socio-political and cultural life of the Turkestan region, but were left out of research due to the ideology of the Soviet era, in these processes, and his intellectual assessment of the events in Afghanistan, have not been studied as a holistic system. Although the influence of Tatar enlightenment on Turkestan by Ismail Gasprinsky, Rizoiddin Fakhreddin and others has been widely covered in historiography, the question of how they analyzed the geopolitical dynamics in Afghanistan has not been addressed. In recent centuries, when a period of decline and depression began in the Islamic world, when Islamic states were being crushed under the terrible oppression of Europeans, only two independent Islamic countries (Turkey, Afghanistan) were not colonized.

Only Turkey and Afghanistan retained some degree of independence and autonomy from the Islamic governments. While their countries remained politically sound with their regular schools, their education and their soldiers armed with the righteous of their time, on the other hand, relying on the power of such a non-existent army, the zeal of the disciplined brave Afghan devotees, and the actions of the kings, the geography of the country's position remained completely free. At the beginning of the 16th century, the British came to India, established a government under the name of the "British India Company" and began to conquer the Rajputana and Gujarat rajas in the south and central part of India, as well as the north and west. They began to invade

Afghan lands through Kashmir and Kafiristan. However, the Afghans, in alliance with the northern Indian rajas, resisted the British. Since the 18th century, the British have sent a number of large armies to Afghanistan, but have been defeated each time. At that time, Afghanistan itself was plagued by throne disputes, tribal conflicts, and quarrels between emirs and khans, so the cunning British used these mischiefs to sometimes occupy Afghanistan. But the Afghan patriots revolted, that is, formed an alliance and drove out their enemies. Thus, Afghanistan changed hands several times. In 1852, the British defeated the rajas on the banks of the Indus River and completely conquered these territories. They conquered Kilatgiljay, which was in the south of Afghanistan, and added it to their protectorate under the name of the Baluchistan Khanate, but Afghanistan retained its independence due to the extraordinary zeal and patriotism of the Afghans and the experienced and skillful policies of the emirs. The British fought with the Afghans for two centuries. However, their efforts to rule the Afghans as they had ruled the Indians were unsuccessful. The British-Afghan struggle ended with the British leaving Afghanistan in the end.

4. DISCUSSION

The results obtained show that the Tatar enlightener Mukhtar Bakir's high attention to the socio-political processes taking place in Afghanistan was not just a curiosity or a desire to observe the outside world, but was a logical part of his integrated anti-colonial and enlightening strategy. The uniqueness of Mukhtar Bakir's work lies in the fact that he was able to successfully connect the advanced intellectual achievements of Tatar Jadidism with the traditional and rather difficult socio-political environment of the Turkestan region. He deeply analyzed the fact that the Emirate of Bukhara and the Khanate of Khiva, under the protectorate of the Russian Empire, retained their independence only in name, but in practice were completely without rights before the tsarist authorities. Bakir always presented Afghanistan as an alternative option in his speeches and notes. He presented the following logical conclusion to the people:

When the Jadids proposed opening New Usul schools in Turkestan, they encountered fierce resistance and slander from local traditionalist scholars and fanatics, who said, "They want to destroy religion and turn children into infidels." Mukhtar Bakir skillfully used the Afghan experience to overcome this ideological barrier. He demonstrated that reforms in Afghanistan were carried out in direct collaboration with religious emirs and Islamic scholars, without contradicting Sharia law, but through the adoption of European science. In his analysis, Bakir demonstrated that the secret of Afghanistan's ability to resist the British invaders lay not only in their religious faith but also in the acquisition of modern weapons, military tactics, and secular knowledge. This logic served as the most powerful argument for the Jadids of Turkestan to persuade believers to engage in internal dialogue. In his geopolitical observations, Mukhtar Bakir viewed the fate of Afghanistan as inextricably linked to the fate of all the peoples of the East, particularly the national liberation movement of Turkestan. Along with criticizing the brutal actions of British imperialism in India and Afghanistan, he also indirectly exposed the colonial policies of Tsarist Russia in Turkestan. Although Mukhtar Bakir wrote about "Britain's oppression of Afghanistan" to circumvent censorship, he was actually seeking to evoke in the reader an analogy with "Russia's oppression of Turkestan." His "Aesopian" journalism served as a powerful intellectual catalyst in the formation of an anti-colonialist worldview among progressive youth in Turkestan.

5. CONCLUSION

The sociopolitical processes unfolding in Afghanistan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, along with efforts to centralize and modernize statehood, were deeply studied and conceptually assessed by the Tatar educator Mukhtar Bakir and the Jadid movement to which he

belonged. As a prominent representative of the Tatar school of education, Mukhtar Bakir successfully transferred and transformed the international and pan-Muslim geopolitical views laid out by Ismail Gasprinsky into the real socio-cultural conditions of the Turkestan region. In Mukhtar Bakir's interpretation, Afghanistan is the only regional example that, under pressure and siege from the participants in the "Great Game" of great empires, retained its political independence and serves as the first spiritual and political center for the awakening of ideas of national statehood and freedom for the intelligentsia and people of Turkestan. Mukhtar Baqir viewed reforms in education, the Siraj ul-Akhbar press, and the military in Afghanistan as a balanced synthesis of traditional religious values and secular sciences. He believed this model was the only way to overcome religious prejudices and administrative stagnation in Turkestan, expand the network of new usul schools, and preserve the nation. In conclusion, Mukhtar Baqir's views on Afghanistan fully demonstrate that he was not only an enlightened educator but also an outstanding public figure and strategist, capable of deeply analyzing international relations and geopolitical processes.

REFERENCES

1. L. Dupree, "The Durand Line of 1993: A Case Study in Artificial Political Boundaries and Culture Areas," in *Current Problems in Afghanistan*, Princeton, 1961, pp. 77-93.
2. Tarziy M. *Analysis of the Afghan newspaper Siraj ul-Akhbar and its socio-political articles (Collection 1911–1919)*. – Kabul, 1920.
3. Behbudiy M. *Selected Works. Two volumes*. – Tashkent: Ma'naviyat, 1999. – V. 1. – P. 90-115.
4. Ismail Gasprinsky. Cholera epidemic. The plague that spread in Afghanistan spread to Turkestan and the Caucasus; about measures against it // *Tarjimon*. June 24 1892 year. № 23
5. Ismail Gasprinsky. To the attention of pilgrims of Turkestan // *Tarjimon*. № 75, 23.09.1905
6. Mukhtar Bakir. *Afghanistan // Ulug Turkestan*. 1918 year. April 2. № 77.
7. A. H. McMahon, "The Southern Borderland of Afghanistan," *The Geographical Journal* 9/4, 1897, pp. 393-426.
8. Mukhtar Bakir. *Afghanistan IV // Ulug Turkestan*. 1918 year. May 25. № 96
9. Mukhtar Bakir. *Afghanistan IX // Ulug Turkestan*. 1918 year. July 2. № 111